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Effect of Dietary Exposure to Carbendazim and Imidacloprid on Biochemicals, Oxidative Stress and Neurotoxicity in Albino Mice

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Abstract

The toxicological interaction of fungicide (carbendazim: CBZ) and insecticide (imidacloprid: IMI) was evaluated using a mouse model system. Mice received IMI-L & IMI-H (45.5 & 90.0 mg/kg feed, respectively), CBZ-L & CBZ-H (1.4 and 2.8g/kg feed, respectively) and in combination (IMI-L+CBZ-L) through the feed. Various toxicological endpoints were evaluated, including feed and water consumption, biochemical parameters, oxidative stress, antioxidants, and neurotoxicity, and the interactive index was calculated. A decrease in feed and water consumption and body weight loss was noticed in CBZ and IMI-treated groups and in combination. A significant change in cytotoxicity biochemical indicators was noticed in IMI and CBZ alone-treated groups as compared to control and combined (IMI-L+CBZ-L) treated groups. Non-significant changes ($p \geq 0.05$) in oxidative stress biomarkers and antioxidants were observed in the IMI-L+CBZ-L group compared with the respective alone-treated groups. Plasma and brain, AChE activity was significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) altered in IMI-L+CBZ-L group when compared with IMI-L and CBZ-L alone groups. Motor activity (FLA and SLA) significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) decreased in IMI and CBZ-treated groups as compared to the combined group. Response to pain significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) increased in IMI and CBZ alone groups when compared with the control and IMI-L+CBZ-L groups. The interactive index calculated for the parameters under investigation indicates the majority of antagonism. The present study suggests that IMI and CBZ exposure via the dietary medium has a dose-dependent toxic effect, but the existence of both in a dietary medium does not lead to additivity or synergism.

Keywords: Carbendazim, Imidacloprid, Oxidative stress, Antioxidants, Neurotoxicity, Interactive Index

Introduction

A pesticide is a chemical agent intended to avoid pests such as insects, bacteria, fungi, nematodes, plants, rodents and many more pests on plants and animals (Lonare et al., 2014). The development of pesticides started during World War II, as there was an urgent need to enhance food production and to find potential chemical warfare agents. Consequently, pesticide use in agriculture was found to be advantageous without apprehension of the potential risks to the environment and human health. The demand for synthetic pesticides has been increasing day by

day due to intensified agricultural farming to meet the requirements of human and animal demand. Despite their popularity and extensive use, pesticides have serious concerns about health risks arising from exposure, such as environmental deprivation and compromise in the quality of soil and water (Vanspati and Tripathi, 2025; Bajaj and Rani, 2025; George et al., 2025; Lonare et al., 2016). Direct exposure is responsible for casualties, while indirect exposure is responsible for health hazards among exposed populations. The health hazards include cardiovascular, respiratory, neurological, endocrine cancer, reproductive disorders, low immunity, and high incidences of diabetes (Mahajan and Randhawa, 2023; Darcin and Darcin, 2017). They may be responsible for the imbalance between endogenous antioxidants and reactive oxygen species generation. Subsequently decreases antioxidant defences in biological systems to cause oxidative stress, tissue damage, and inflammation, giving rise to diseases and ageing (Valavanidis et al., 2006).

Carbendazim (CBZ; methyl-2-benzimidazole carbamate) is a systemic fungicide of the benzimidazole class of pesticides (Durand et al., 2017). It is one of the most commonly used fungicides in the agricultural sector for fruit preservation; crop protection from decay caused by fungal infestations. It's used extensively as a wood preservative in the fibre, paper, and leather industries (Patil et al., 2023; Beg et al., 2024). The use of CBZ has increased several-fold in recent years, and potential risks associated with studies have been published. It has major deleterious effects on sexual maturity, the development of the foetus, hormonal regulation, and testicular cell damage (Cevik et al., 2017, Durand et al., 2017). Whereas imidacloprid (IMI), is the first member of the neonicotinoid group of insecticides invented in 1985 and is known for its extensive use as an insecticide worldwide (Wang et al., 2018). IMI acts as an agonist on nicotinic acetylcholine (nAChRs) receptors of the insect and a partial agonist in mammals. The reports pertaining to the adverse effects of IMI increased with a sudden rise in their application in agro-vet-practices, hence traces being noticed in samples collected from humans and urine in recent years from many countries (Wang et al., 2020). IMI use has been increased, looking towards specificity against insects, thus, exposure level to the non-targeted animal species has been increased. Adverse effects resulting from their exposure, such as teratogenicity, mutagenicity, neurotoxicity, reproductive toxicity, and immunotoxicity, have been reported (Ndonwi et al., 2019).

The application of more than one pesticide during a single-crop or multi-crop cultivation practice in agriculture is very common. Thus, complex residues remain in a variety of media and food commodities. They may produce toxic effects through the consumption of grains, feed, fodder and/or contaminated water (Beg et al., 2024) on millions of non-target animal species, human beings, animals, birds and aquatic species. Long-term exposure to a mixture may lead to unpredictable toxic effects. However, assessment of the potential health hazards of the chemical mixture is difficult and a challenging toxicological problem, leading to a subject of major concern to the scientific and regulatory communities (Mansour et al., 2008). Many researchers have explored the interactive effect of toxicants based on oxidative stress, enzymatic effects, antioxidant status, inflammatory markers, and neurobehavioral changes (Abolaji et al., 2017, Ndonwi et al., 2019). The joint action of chemical mixtures can be estimated qualitatively and quantitatively based on experimental data from exposure to pesticide mixtures and/or individual components (Mansour and Refaie, 2000; Singh et al., 2023). To date, no evidence is available on the interactive effects of CBZ and IMI co-exposure in animals and humans. Considering the present facts, we feel there is an urgency to establish the basic data that indicate the effect of CBZ on IMI toxicosis or vice versa. Therefore, the present study was planned to investigate the interactive effect of fungicide and insecticide using an effective mouse model system.

Materials and methods

Chemicals and reagents

Technical grade carbendazim (97%) was procured from Sigma Aldrich, USA. Imidacloprid (94 %) was a kind of gift received from M/s Gharda Chemicals, Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai. All the chemicals of analytical grade and enzymes used in the present study were obtained from established firms (Sigma, Bangalore-Genei, Himedia, Merck, and Span Diagnostics Pvt. Ltd., India).

Feed formulation and feeding

Selected dosages of test compounds (mg/kg body weight) were converted into the dose required through feed (mg/kg feed) by the standard formula (Lehman, 1954). Standard animal feed was ground to a fine powder. The technical grade test compounds were dissolved in the required quantity of acetone with different concentrations (Table 1) and sprinkled on the powder form of

feed. Finally, pellets were prepared, dried, and stored in an air tied container until used. Control group feed was also formulated similarly, only the vehicle was added. These pelleted feeds were fed to the animals during experimentation.

Procurement, maintenance and ethical approval of experimental animals

A total of sixty male Swiss Albino mice weighing about 25-30 gm were procured from the National Institute of Pharmaceutical Education and Research (NIPER), Mohali, Punjab. Mice were housed in the Laboratory Experimental House of GADVASU, Ludhiana, and maintained in polyacrylic cages throughout the experiment. During the experiment, animals were maintained under standard managemental practices, which include pelleted feed (Ashirwad Pvt Ltd, Mohali Punjab) and water ad-libitum with 12h light and 12h dark cycle with 22 ± 3 °C room temperature. Before the start of the experiment, the experimental protocol was approved by the Institutional Animal Ethics Committee of the College of Veterinary Science, Guru Angad Dev Veterinary and Animal Sciences University, Ludhiana, India (GADVASU/2018/IAEC/47/08). All experiments have been carried out in accordance with the guidelines of the Committee for the Purpose of Control and Supervision of Experiments on Animals (CPCSEA), New Delhi, India.

Table 1. Experimental design for in vivo sub-acute toxicity study in male mice.

Groups	Treatments	Standard Dose (mg/kg b.wt., PO)	Dose conversion for feed (ppm; mg/kg feed)
I	Control	-	Normal feed
II	IMI-L	6.5 mg/kg	45.5 mg/kg feed
III	IMI-H	13 mg/kg	91.0 mg/kg feed
IV	CBZ-L	200 mg/kg	1.4g/kg feed
V	CBZ-H	400 mg/kg	2.8 g/kg feed
VI	CBZ-L+IMI-L	6.5mg/kg+200mg/kg	45mg/kg+1.4g/kg

* IMI: imidacloprid; CBZ: carbendazim; L:Low; H: High

Experimental design

Mice were assigned to the different test groups based on a random sort program. Sixty male mice were randomly divided into six groups of 10 animals each. Group I served as control. Group II and, III were treated with a high and low dose of imidacloprid (IMI), respectively. Group IV and V were treated with a high and low dose of carbendazim (CBZ), respectively. Group VI was treated with a combination of low-dose IMI and low-dose CBZ. All animals received normal and test compounds for 28 days through the feed (Table 1).

Signs and symptoms of toxicity

All animals were observed two times a day throughout the experiment to see any signs and symptoms of toxicity, if any, such as a change in gross observed behavior, motor activity, hyperactivity, tremor, convulsions, diarrhea, dyspnoea, and death.

Water and feed intake

The intake of water and feed was recorded, and the total requirement was calculated every fourth nightly basis. Pre-weighed food and pre-measured water were delivered in cage hoppers and water bottled and leftover was removed after the next day. Intake was measured as the weight of the food given (grams) minus the feed retrieved from the hopper. Similarly, in the feeding water bottles a fixed volume of water was provided, and the next day the water intake was calculated as the (mL) of water recovered less the total volume of water provided.

Body weight and weight gain

The body weights of all rats were recorded every fourth day from day zero before the start of the experiment till the completion of the experiment. Percent weight gain or weight loss was calculated at end of the experiment using the formula

$$\text{Percent body weight gain} = \frac{\text{Final body weight (g)} - \text{Initial body weight (g)}}{\text{Initial body weight (g)}} \times 100$$

Blood collection and estimation of enzymatic activity

Experimental mice were killed after the completion of the last dose. Blood samples were collected in tubes containing heparin from all the mice, directly from the heart under proper anesthesia. The plasma was separated and used for the evaluation of the enzymatic activity. Commercial biochemical kits were procured from ERBA Diagnostics Mannheim GmbH manufactured by Transasia Bio-Medicals Ltd. Mumbai, India for the estimation of lactate dehydrogenase (LDH), alkaline phosphatase (ALP), creatine kinase (CK), and gamma-glutamyltransferase (GGT) activity. Sample collection and preparation of tissue homogenates. The vital organs were collected immediately after the sacrifice of the animals from different groups. Tissues weighed were recorded (gm) and relative organ weights were calculated. The brain samples were stored under -200C until used for oxidative stress parameters. The brain was also preserved in 10% formal buffer saline for histopathological evaluation.

The brains were weighed and 10% tissue homogenate was prepared by tissue homogenizer (IKA® T25 digital ultra Turrax®) in ice-cold PBS (8gm/L NaCl, 0.20gm/L KCl, 1.44 gm/L Na₂HPO₄.2H₂O and 0.24gm/L KH₂PO₄). The pH was adjusted to 7.4 using 0.1N NaOH and 0.1N HCl solutions. Estimation of reduced glutathione (GSH) level, and tissue homogenate was prepared in a 0.02 M EDTA solution. The homogenates were centrifuged for 10 min at 3000 rpm at 40C and the supernatant was collected and stored at -20 oC until used for AChE and biochemical estimations.

Table 2. Effect of IMI, CBZ alone and their combination per os on daily feed consumption (g) in male mice

Groups	Treatments	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	Average
I	Control	3.13	3.65	5.00	7.50	6.30	6.29	7.09	5.56
II	IMI-L	3.19	3.86	4.41	6.35	5.90	6.02	6.61	5.19
III	IMI-H	2.66	3.44	4.43	5.98	5.79	5.68	6.56	4.93
IV	CBZ-L	2.94	3.89	4.41	6.25	6.19	5.91	6.76	5.19
V	CBZ-H	2.80	3.79	4.36	6.09	6.05	5.33	5.79	4.89
VI	IMI-L+CBZ-L	2.84	3.61	4.78	6.04	5.66	5.58	6.59	5.01

*I-VII are intervals and each interval consist of four days. Values are feed consumption by the animal per day. Groups I & VI (n=10); Groups II-V (n=11). IMI: Imidacloprid, CBZ: Carbendazim.

Estimation of oxidative stress indicators and anti-oxidant enzymes

Lipid peroxidation (LPO) was estimated as per the published method of Stocks and Dormandy (1971), while, superoxide anion radicals (O₂.-) were measured by the method of Wang et al., (1998). Nitrite (NO₂-), a stable oxidation product of NO, was analyzed in the brain by the method of Sastry et al., (2002). Reduced glutathione (GSH) and total thiol levels were measured by the method of Beutler (1963). Total protein was measured as the published method by Lowry et al., (1951). Antioxidant enzymes activity was measured as per the standard spectrophotometric method, SOD activity by Madesh and Balsubramaniam (1998), GST activity by Habig et al. (1974), GPx activity by Hafeman et al., (1974), and CAT activity by Aebi (1984). AChE was measured by spectrophotometric assay, as described by Ellman et al. (1961), in blood plasma and brain homogenate.

Neurobehavioural Analysis

With the completion of the exposure period, the neurotoxicity end parameters were evaluated in all the groups.

General behavioural profiles

The animals were under monitoring at 30 min intervals in the first two hours and at hourly intervals for the next 4 hours for the behavioral changes and signs of harmful effects, if any. At the end of the experiment, the sensitivity, alertness, and reaction to the touch were registered and scored accordingly.

Measurement of motor function

Spontaneous Locomotor Activity (SLA) was analyzed using photosensitive cages (photo-actometer monitors, MAC Microscientifics, MSW-738). Mice were put in the middle of the cages in dark and left unchanged for 5 min test sessions and a complete digital show operation was registered for their locomotor activity. While forced locomotor activity (FLA) was measured using an automatic spinning rod with a rota-rod system. Mice were allowed to run after setting rota-rod and were tested three times. Individual animals were put on the rotating rod and the total time spent on the revolving rod was measured within five minutes (Dunham and Miya, 1957). Grip

strength, the gripping power of muscles to hold tension by limbs, was measured with the help of a digital Grip-Strength meter (UGO Basile, Germany).

Measurement of pain threshold

An increase in body temperature results in sensitization of thermoregulatory core activation and consequently the HPA axis (Kvetnansky et al., 1971). Cold Allodynia was measured using the cold water tail immersion test, the most widely used method ($40\text{C} \pm 10\text{C}$). The reaction time, considered as the efforts made to eliminate the tail, was measured in second(s). Whereas hot allodynia was measured using a hot water tail immersion test ($55\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 10\text{C}$). The reaction time was measured in a similar fashion as that of cold allodynia. Further, hyper-algesia was assessed by plate test (Woolfe and MacDonald, 1944) using Eddy's hot plate having $56\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 10\text{C}$ temperature. Reaction time was indicated by paw licking and jumping.

Histopathology

The tissue samples (brain) were immediately collected after sacrifice in 10% formalin for fixation. The fixed tissues were processed through ascending grades of alcohol, followed by xylene and paraffin embedding as per the standard operating protocol. Tissue sections were obtained at 3-4 μm thickness and Hematoxylin and Eosin staining (Luna, 1968) was performed. The stained slides were mounted with coverslip using DPX mountant and examined under a bright-field microscope for histopathological interpretations.

Measurement of Interactive Index

An interactive index was calculated for the different parameters to see the types of effect by Mansour's formula (Mansour and Refaie, 2000) to identify the type of interaction between pair of toxicants termed as Interaction Index (I.I.) ($I.I. = M + C/A_1 + A_2$; Where: M, C, A₁ & A₂ represent the mean values obtained from the estimated studied parameter. M is the value of the mixture or combination-treated group; A₁ & A₂ for the values of the individual or alone compounds treated group and C for the value of the control group). In case of positive effect (C value above the control values due to the effect of the individual compounds), then $I.I. > 1$: potentiation; $I.I. = 1$: additive; $I.I. < 1$: antagonism. In case of a negative effect (Decrease in the C value below the control values due to the effect of the individual compounds), then $I.I. > 1$: antagonism; $I.I. = 1$: additive; $I.I. < 1$: potentiation.

Statistical analysis

All the data was compiled and comparisons among different groups were made using statistical design using IBM SPSS Statistics, Version 2.0 statistical software, and Microsoft Excel. All the data were compared by employing one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) with Tukey's multiple comparisons as a post hoc test. A p-value of < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Effect on in-life parameters

One mortality along with slight hair fall at the snout or nasal area and rough body coat, was noticed in the IMI-H treated group. These changes were quite prominent from mid to the end of the experiment. No other apparent signs of toxicity were noticed in mice from the treatment and control groups.

Effect on feed and water intake

During the first four days, all the treatment groups showed comparatively lower average feed intake but a prominent change in feed consumption was observed after 8 days of feeding. IMI, CBZ alone and IMI-L+CBZ-L treated groups showed a comparative decrease in the average feed consumption. IMI-H and CBZ-H showed comparatively significant changes in feed consumption when compared with all other groups (Table 2).

Average water consumption was comparatively decreased in all the treatment groups when compared to the control group from day 8 onward. Very low water consumption was recorded from IMI-H and CBZ-H alone-treated groups on 6th and 7th intervals as compared to control, IMI-L, CBZ-L alone, and their combination-treated groups (Table 3).

Effect on body weight and brain weight

Significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) less body weight was measured on day 28 in CBZ-L and IMI-H as compared to the control group. Feeding of CBZ and IMI and their combination resulted in significant ($p \leq$

0.05) weight loss/gain and percent weight loss/gain in CBZ and IMI alone-treated groups as compared to the control and IMI-L+CBZ-L combined treated group (Fig. 1).

Table 3. Effect of IMI, CBZ alone and their combination per os on daily water consumption (ml) in male mice.

Groups	Treatments	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	Final Average
I	Control	4.20	4.43	6.36	8.68	9.77	5.86	11.48	7.26
II	IMI-L	4.20	3.41	3.64	6.20	5.45	5.91	8.64	5.35
III	IMI-H	3.95	4.32	4.09	6.34	4.36	3.50	3.86	4.35
IV	CBZ-L	4.54	4.68	5.40	7.55	7.84	5.57	9.57	6.45
V	CBZ-H	4.20	3.41	3.64	6.20	5.45	3.50	3.86	4.32
VI	IMI-L+CBZ-L	3.50	3.50	5.00	6.12	6.87	5.75	9.13	5.69

* I-VII are intervals and each interval is of four days. Values are an average of four days and water consumed per animal per day. Groups I & VI (n=10); Groups II-V (n=11). IMI: Imidacloprid, CBZ: Carbendazim

Non-significant ($p > 0.05$) change in the absolute and relative brain and heart weight was observed between CBZ and IMI alone, in combination, and in control groups. Significant change ($p < 0.05$) in absolute and relative organ weights between different groups was noticed for the liver, kidney and, testes and epididymis (Table 4).

Table 4. Effect on absolute organ and relative organ weights (g) after exposure to CBZ, IMI alone and their combination per os in mice.

Treatments (Groups)	Weights	Liver	Lung	Kidney	Heart	Brain	Testes+Epididymis
Control (I)	AOW	1.16±0.010 ^a	0.175±0.005 ^a	0.351±0.009 ^{ab}	0.158±0.006 ^a	0.420±0.007 ^a	0.341±0.005 ^a
	ROW	3.548±0.120 ^a	0.609±0.035 ^a	3.935±0.169 ^a	1.935±0.094 ^a	4.714±0.264 ^a	4.530±0.213 ^a
IMI-L (II)	AOW	1.37±0.036 ^c	0.230±0.011 ^c	0.375±0.011 ^{bc}	0.158±0.009 ^a	0.439±0.008 ^a	0.444±0.009 ^{bc}
	ROW	4.343±0.135 ^b	0.768±0.049 ^b	4.153±0.112 ^a	1.761±0.100 ^a	4.909±0.249 ^a	5.888±0.511 ^a
IMI-H (III)	AOW	1.27±0.018 ^b	0.221±0.005 ^c	0.367±0.006 ^{bc}	0.173±0.004 ^a	0.413±0.011 ^a	0.466±0.009 ^c
	ROW	4.299±0.159 ^b	0.738±0.053 ^{ab}	4.554±0.104 ^a	2.048±0.082 ^a	4.956±0.237 ^a	5.815±0.413 ^a
CBZ-L (IV)	AOW	1.25±0.013 ^b	0.203±0.008 ^{ab}	0.338±0.013 ^{ab}	0.163±0.005 ^a	0.420±0.013 ^a	0.461±0.005 ^c
	ROW	4.575±0.149 ^b	0.729±0.017 ^{ab}	4.339±0.117 ^a	2.110±0.089 ^a	5.461±0.279 ^a	5.088±0.565 ^a
CBZ-H (V)	AOW	1.22±0.014 ^{ab}	0.181±0.004 ^a	0.316±0.006 ^a	0.168±0.008 ^a	0.425±0.006 ^a	0.429±0.009 ^b
	ROW	4.375±0.223 ^b	0.639±0.019 ^{ab}	3.991±0.194 ^a	2.119±0.157 ^a	5.388±0.174 ^a	5.114±0.181 ^a
IMI-L+CBZ-L (VI)	AOW	1.40±0.022 ^c	0.235±0.009 ^c	0.388±0.006 ^c	0.161±0.006 ^a	0.433±0.003 ^a	0.521±0.004 ^d
	ROW	4.423±0.178 ^b	0.741±0.029 ^{ab}	4.163±0.248 ^a	1.711±0.097 ^a	4.526±0.268 ^a	5.589±0.564 ^a

Values (Mean ± SEM, n=8) bearing different superscripts in the same column differ significantly ($p < 0.05$) in Tukey's multiple comparison post hoc test. CBZ: carbendazim, IMI: imidacloprid, AOW: absolute organ weight (g); ROW: relative organ weight (g/100g b. wt.)

Effect on biochemicals

ALP levels in IMI-L+CBZ-L treated mice were significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) higher than IMI-L group, while significantly lower than CBZ-L treated group. LDH levels in IMI-L+CBZ-L treated mice were significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) less than IMI-L group, while significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) higher than CBZ-L treated group. GGT values in IMI-L+CBZ-L treated mice were significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) higher as compared to IMI-L and CBZ-L alone treated groups. Significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) lower value of CK-MB was noticed in the IMI-L+CBZ-L combined group when compared with the IMI-L and CBZ-L treatment group (Fig. 2). A significant decrease ($p \leq 0.05$) in the plasma and brain AChE activity in CBZ, IMI alone, and IMI-L+CBZ-L treated groups was noticed as compared to the control group. Plasma AChE activity did not differ significantly in IMI-L+CBZ-L treated mice when compared with IMI-L alone treated mice, whereas, differed significantly when compared with CBZ-L alone treated mice (Fig. 3).

Effect on oxidative stress indicators

A significant increase ($p < 0.05$) in the LPO was noticed in IMI, CBZ alone, and combination-treated groups when compared with the control group in the brain. IMI-L+CBZ-L treated group showed significantly more as compared to IMI-L and CBZ-L alone treated groups. A dose-dependent increase in the level of LPO was noticed in CBZ and IMI-treated groups (Fig. 4a). A significant increase ($p \leq 0.05$) in superoxide radical anion brains was noticed in IMI, CBZ alone, and in combination-treated groups when compared with the control group. A significant and dose-dependent increase in the O₂-radical was noticed between IMI and CBZ alone-treated groups (Fig. 4b).

Nitrite concentration in the brain was significantly increased ($p \leq 0.05$) in CBZ, IMI alone, and combination-treated groups in a dose-dependent manner as compared to the control group. The IMI-L+CBZ-L treatment showed non-significantly higher and significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) higher nitrite levels as compared to IMI-L and CBZ-L groups, respectively (Fig. 4c).

The brain tissue protein level of the IMI-L+CBZ-L group was significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) less as compared to IMI-L and CBZ-L groups. Tissue protein concentration was significantly decreased ($p \leq 0.05$) in CBZ, IMI alone, and their combination (IMI-L+CBZ-L) treated groups in a dose-dependent manner as compared to the control group (Fig. 4d).

Effect on the endogenous antioxidant level

SOD and GPx activity was significantly decreased ($p \leq 0.05$) in the CBZ, IMI alone and combination-treated groups in a dose-dependent manner when compared with the control group. SOD activity in the IMI-L+CBZ-L combination group was significantly higher than CBZ-L and lower than IMI-L treated group (Fig. 5a&b). GPx activity was significantly lower in the IMI-L+CBZ-L treated group as compared to IMI-L and CBZ-L alone treated group. IMI-L+CBZ-L treatment caused a significant decrease in CAT activity as compared to the IMI-alone treated group, while significantly higher than the CBZ-L alone treated group (Fig. 5d).

Dietary exposure of CBZ, IMI alone, and their combination resulted in a significant decrease ($p \leq 0.05$) in GSH, and total thiol levels as compared to control groups (Fig. 5c). The brain GSH level was significantly higher in IMI-L+CBZ-L treated groups when compared with IMI-L and CBZ-L alone treated groups. The total thiol level of the brain was significantly higher in CBZ-L and IMI-L groups as compared to the IMI-L+CBZ-L group (Fig. 5e).

Spontaneous locomotor activity (SLA)

A dose-dependent and significant decrease ($p \leq 0.05$) in the SLA of IMI, CBZ alone, and the combined treated group was noticed as compared to the control group. The IMI-L+CBZ-L treated group showed significantly lower SLA as compared to IMI-L and CBZ-L alone treated groups (Table 5).

Table 5. Effect of carbendazim, imidacloprid alone and their combination on spontaneous SLA, FLA and grip strength in mice.

Groups	Treatments	SLA	FLA	Grip strength
I	Control	55.43±0.280 ^f	68.75±0.860 ^e	673.50±0.866 ^f
II	IMI-L	46.73±1.06 ^e	26.62±0.595 ^b	595.00±1.180 ^b
III	IMI-H	38.29±0.426 ^d	18.87±0.515 ^a	571.03±0.476 ^a
IV	CBZ-L	33.21±0.472 ^c	28.75±0.796 ^b	613.27±0.288 ^d
V	CBZ-H	23.43±0.604 ^a	53.75±0.881 ^d	603.76±2.497 ^c
VI	IMI-L+CBZ-L	26.51±1.00 ^b	32.37±0.943 ^c	622.50±0.866 ^e

Values (Mean ± SEM, n=8) bearing different superscripts in the same column differ significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) in Tukey's multiple comparison post hoc test. CBZ: carbendazim, IMI: imidacloprid, SLA: spontaneous locomotor activity; FLA: force locomotor activity.

Table 6. Comparative analysis of severity of changes in the brain on histopathological investigation in IMI, CBZ alone and combination exposed mice.

Severity of tissue changes	Pathologic parameters	Control	IMI-L	IMI-H	CBZ-L	CBZ-H	IMI-L+CBZ-L
Mild	Congestion of meningeal blood vessels	+	+ / ++	++	++	+	+ / ++
	Meningeal edema	---	---	+	++	+	+ / ++
Moderate	Mononuclear cell infiltration in meninges	---	+	+	+	--	+
	Gliosis (glial cell proliferation)	---	+	++	- / +	++	+
Marked	Parenchymal loss of white mater and neuropil vacuolation (vacuolation)	---	---	---	---	+	---

IMI: imidacloprid; CBZ: carbendazim. + : Mild changes; ++: Moderate changes; + ++: Marked changes; - / +: Occasional (rare) changes; + / ++: Mild to moderate changes; ---: No changes noted

Force locomotor activity (FLA)

A significant decrease ($p \leq 0.05$) in the average time spent was noticed in all IMI, CBZ alone, and their combination-treated groups when compared with the control group. IMI-L+CBZ-L treated

mice showed significantly higher ($p \leq 0.05$) activity as compared to IMI-L and CBZ alone-treated mice (Table 5). Dose-dependent and a significant decrease in the time spent on the rotating rod was noticed between IMI and CBZ alone-treated groups.

Table 7. Effect on the interactive index (II) with dietary exposure of IMI, CBZ and their combination on different parameters studied.

Weight gain (g)	% weight gain	Feed Intake	Water Intake	ALP	LDH	CK-MB	AChE Plasma
(-ve)	(-ve)	(-ve)	(-ve)	(+ve)	(+ve)	(+ve)	(-ve)
-2.14	-1.92	1.02	1.10	0.93	0.97	0.83	1.50
AN	AN	AD	AN	AN	AN	AN	AN
AChE Brain	LPO	O ² -radical	Nitric oxide	Total protein	SOD (-ve)	GPx	GSH
(-ve)	(+ve)	(+ve)	(+ve)	(-ve)		(-ve)	(-ve)
1.27	0.92	0.63	0.80	1.17	1.37	3.55	1.32
AN	AN	AN	AN	AN	AN	AN	AN
CAT	Total thiols	Grip strength test	Hot plate test		Tail immersion test		
			Reaction time	No. of Jumps	Hot water	Cold water	
(-ve)	(+/-ve)	(-ve)	(+ve)	(-ve)	(+ve)	(+ve)	
1.43	0.76	1.07	0.79	1.87	0.89	1.03	
AN	PO	AN	AN	AN	AN	AD	

Numerical values indicate type of interaction and interactive index. AN: antagonism; AD: additive; PO: potentiation. Positive (+) and negative (-) signs are indicative of the effect drugs have on particular parameters with respect to control.

Fig. 1. Effect on percent body and weight gain (%) with exposure to IMI, CBZ alone and their combination per os in male mice.

Values (Mean \pm SEM, $n=8$) bearing different superscripts in the same column differ significantly ($p < 0.05$) in Tukey's multiple comparison post hoc test. CBZ: carbendazim, IMI: imidacloprid, oD: o day, 28D: 28 day.

Fig. 2. Effect of carbendazim, imidacloprid alone and their combination on biochemical parameters of mice.

Values (Mean \pm SEM, $n=3$) bearing different superscripts in the same column differ significantly ($p < 0.05$) in Tukey's multiple comparison post hoc test. CBZ: carbendazim, IMI: imidacloprid, ALP: Alkaline phosphatase; LDH: Lactate dehydrogenase; GGT: Gamma-glutamyl transferase. CK-MB: Creatine kinase

Fig. 3. Effect of carbendazim, imidacloprid alone and their combination on AChE in plasma, and brain in mice.

Values (Mean ± SEM, n=4(brain) n=3(plasma)) bearing different superscripts in the same column differ significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) in Tukey's multiple comparison post hoc test. CBZ: carbendazim, IMI: imidacloprid; AChE: Acetylcholinesterase. Unit: (μM butyrylthiocholine hydrolysed/ min/ ml or g) of plasma/ tissue.

Fig. 4. Effect of IMI, CBZ alone and their combination on oxidative stress indicators in brain of mice.

Values (Mean ± SEM, n=4) bearing different superscripts in the same column differ significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) in Tukey's multiple comparison post hoc test. CBZ: carbendazim, IMI: imidacloprid. LPO: Unit for tissue lysate: nmol MDA/g tissue. O₂ radicle: Unit for tissue lysate: pmol/min/mg protein; NO (nitric oxide) Unit for tissue: nmole/g of wet tissue; total protein: Unit for tissue: mg/g tissue

Grip strength

A significant decrease ($p \leq 0.05$) in the grip strength was measured in IMI and CBZ alone and IMI-L+CBZ-L treated mice when compared with control mice. IMI-L+CBZ-L treated mice showed significantly higher grip strength as compared to IMI-L and CBZ-L alone treated mice (Table 5).

Effect on sensory parameters

In the hot plate test, the IMI and CBZ alone treated groups showed a significant ($p \leq 0.05$) increase in the reaction time in a dose-dependent manner when compared with control and IMI-L+CBZ-L combination groups. Reaction time or the number of jumps during the observation period significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) decreased in IMI and CBZ alone and their combination-treated groups as compared to the control group (Fig. 6a). In the tail immersion test, reaction time in hot and cold water was significantly ($P < 0.05$) increased in IMI, CBZ alone, and combination-treated groups as compared to the control group (Fig. 6b).

Effect on cellular changes in brain

Control animals revealed no major changes when it was observed microscopically (Fig. 7a). In IMI-treated groups, mild glial cell proliferation (gliosis) and mild thickening of meningeal layers at occasional locations were noted. The hemodynamic (hyperemic and edematous) changes within meningeal blood vessels and cerebral parenchyma appear to be a dose-dependent phenomenon

where moderate congestion of meninges and mild widening of perivascular space (Virchow- Robin space) was present in high-dose treated group (Fig. 7b). In case of CBZ treated groups, the changes were more or less similar to IMI treated groups with additional changes that include focal meningeal thickening with mild MN cell infiltrations, vacuolation (parenchymal loss) of white matter (cerebellum), and indistinct vacuolation of neuropil besides occasional glial cell proliferation. A distinguished dose dependency was also observed in this group, where the extent of cited tissue changes was more in high dose CBZ group (Fig. 7c). In the case of the combined drug-treated group (CBZ-I+IMI-I), the changes oscillated between the two drug-treated groups, where meningeal thickening due to both vascular congestion and cellular infiltration, besides moderate widening of perivascular space (Virchow -Robin space) was observed. In addition to this, mild glial cell proliferation was noted in a few cases (Fig. 7d). No additional significant changes were observed in the combined (CBZ-I+IMI-I) treated group. The microscopically visible changes in the brain were graded and scored. The grading of the changes depended on the various changes visualised in the brain of different groups as an average represented in tabulated form (Table 6).

Interactive Index outcome

The interactive index (II) was calculated for various parameters and showed a majority of antagonism, followed by additive and potentiation (Table 7). The predominant interactive effect was considered to be its major action inside the body of animals, and here we observed an antagonistic effect when CBZ and IMI were collectively present at once in an animal body. They do not work synergistically.

Fig. 5. Effect of IMI, CBZ alone and their combination on antioxidant enzyme system of brain of mice.

Values (Mean \pm SEM, n=4) bearing different superscripts in the same column differ significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) in Tukey's multiple comparison post hoc test. CBZ: carbendazim, IMI: imidacloprid. Unit for tissue: U/ mg protein; GPx: U/ mg protein; GSH: Unit for tissue: $\mu\text{mol/ g tissue}$. Total thio: $\mu\text{mol/ g tissue}$; CAT: $\mu\text{m of H}_2\text{O}_2$ decomposed/ min/mg protein.

Discussion

Exposure to chemical agents through feed and water is a very common and unusual cause of chronic disease production. Long-term ingestion of toxic chemicals that interfere with the growth and weight gain of animals. These parameters serve as a negative physiological indicator of good health. Their exposure is responsible for the induction of toxicopathological conditions that alter the metabolic process and ultimately interfere with body weight gain (Al-Shabanah and Raza

2002, Aly et al., 2009; Patil et al., 2023). The negative effect on body weight gain and decrease in feed and water intake was found to be more in CBZ and IMI alone-treated groups, while less pronounced in the combination group. This could be due to a lack of appetite and a decrease in feed consumption, responsible for the decrease in body weight gain or loss of body weight. That may have a direct toxic effect on liver function, which is the main organ of metabolism. These pesticides caused an adverse effect on liver function and were clearly noticed through an elevated level of liver function and related cytotoxicity indicators. Similarly, a decrease in body weight at higher doses of CBZ-treated animals and weight loss with reduced food intake with altered relative organ weight in IMI-exposed animals have been reported (Najafi et al., 2010; Kapoor et al., 2010; Lonare et al., 2016). Dietary exposure to a pesticide mixture may produce an effect less than or equal to that of the most efficient pesticide that may or may not reflect the combined effects of individual constituents (Demur et al., 2013). Similar observations were made in the present study; the CBZ and IMI combined group does not show the effect on feed and water consumption and weight gain when compared with the individually treated groups.

Fig. 6. Effect of carbendazim, imidacloprid alone and their combination on (a) hot plate test and (b) tail immersion test in mice.

Values (Mean \pm SEM, $n=8$) bearing different superscripts in the same column differ significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) in Tukey's multiple comparison post hoc test. CBZ: carbendazim, IMI: imidacloprid. Unit: seconds.

Pesticide exposure causes ROS generation in cells and leakage of LDH, CK, and, ALP into the surrounding medium, indicating altered cellular function and oxidative tissue damage (Kalender et al., 2006; Jose et al., 2011). LDH activity has a direct correlation with cell damage and an increase in the level of enzymatic activity (Singh et al., 2023). The results of the present study are complementary with previous reports; oral administration of CBZ (Waghe et al., 2013; Salihu et al., 2016; Patil et al., 2023) and IMI (Arfat et al., 2014; Lonare et al., 2016) noticeably elevated plasma levels of ALT, AST, ALP, LDH, GGT and CK in different animal species, indicating damage to the vital organs (Mauro et al., 2006; Patil et al., 2023; Lonare et al., 2016). In the present research, a similar increase in the level of plasma CK, ALP, GGT, and LDH were noticed. This indicates that hepatic and other vital organ damage is produced by the ingestion of IMI and CBZ through the feed.

Pesticides stimulate excess production of ROS generation that leads to alteration in the cellular antioxidant network and thereby increase the susceptibility to lipid peroxidation and oxidative stress, DNA damage, protein degradation, and ultimately vital tissue damage (Lopez et al., 2007; Broznic et al., 2008). Moreover, LPO is used as a biomarker for the prediction of oxidative stress and tissue injury that occurs with exposure to the pesticide (Mansour and Mossa, 2010). The ROS has a direct damaging effect on the target protein and DNA that interferes with cell survival mediated by kinase cascades (Kang and Hamasaki, 2003). In the present study, an increase in the LPO, O_2^- radicals, and nitrite levels in CBZ and IMI alone and in combination groups was noticed. This indicates that CBZ and IMI exposure caused oxidative stress, responsible for LPO (Sakr and Shalaby, 2014, Ge et al., 2015). Similarly, pesticide treatment in male rats enhanced O_2^- -radical levels in the liver, testis and epididymis and in activated phagocytes (Gulcin et al., 2002). Elevated levels of plasma nitric oxide and impaired NOS function of the brain in the presence of pesticides have been reported (El-Gohary et al., 1999; Patil et al., 2023).

SOD is a copper-zinc-containing enzyme that decomposes the superoxide anion to H_2O_2 and then catalyzes to H_2O by CAT and GPx in all vertebrates or is reduced by a GSH-dependent mechanism catalyzed by GPx. The mitochondrial dysfunction altered the SOD production due to elevated concentrations of H_2O_2 and that improved the dismutation of O_2^- through H_2O_2 development (Rohrdanz et al., 2001; Liochev and Fridovich, 2007). The reduction in the GPx with exposure to

toxicants is responsible for the unnecessary harm to vital organs. The presence of significant amounts of pesticides or their residues resulted in the inactivation of the functional enzymatic protein. Lower antioxidant enzymatic activity in CBZ and IMI alone and combined treated group was observed in the present. Congruently, a significant decline in SOD, CAT, GSH and GPx activity in CBZ (Metwally et al., 2011; Patil et al., 2023) and IMI-treated animals has been reported (Kapoor et al., 2010; Salihu et al., 2016).

GSH is the most abundant non-protein thiol and plays a crucial role in intracellular defence against harmful substances. Depletion of intracellular GSH induces degradation and destruction of lipid bilayers, proteins and DNA by the reactive oxygen species (Wang, 2000; Lonare et al., 2016). A decrease in the GSH and protein content in the present study suggests that poor antioxidant status or increased oxidative stress is responsible for the rise in damage to the cell membrane. Likewise, reduced tissue levels of GSH and cell damage to paraquat and CBZ-exposed rats have been observed (Waghe et al., 2013; Ranjan et al., 2014; Patil et al., 2023). Further, exposure to CBZ may result in hepatic damage that contributes to a reduction in protein synthesis (Zari and Al-Attar, 2011).

Fig. 7. Histological architecture of the brain. (a) The brain from control animal showing normal architecture with no major changes. (b) IMI-L treated brain showing gliosis (red oval zone) and congestion of blood vessels (arrows) (c) CBZ-H treated brain showing vacuolation in white matter (red oval zone) and mild glial cell presence after treatment. (d) IMI-L+CBZ-L treated animal brain showing focal meningeal thickening (lepto-meningitis), vascular congestion with mild MN cell infiltrations. (Original Magnification: a & b: x10 H&E; b & c: x20 H&E)

There was a change in the IMI and CBZ treatment groups AChE activities in plasma and brain in the current study. This could be due to exposure to neonicotinoids, altered biochemical processes related to the cholinergic systems and altered AChE activity, accompanied by deficits in behavioral performance (Rodrigues et al., 2010; Patil et al., 2023). Considering the toxic potential of neonicotinoids on nAChRs and inhibition of AChE to alter the BBB mechanisms contributed to their neurotoxicity and altered neurobehavior response of the animals. Moreover, few studies have indicated neonicotinoid exposure could be associated with neurodegeneration, induced cerebellum toxicity, and oxidative stress (Dhouib et al., 2017; Lonare et al., 2014). A decrease in the AChE level after repeated oral administration of IMI in cockerels (Siddiqui et al., 2007) and rats (Bhardwaj et al., 2010; Kapoor et al., 2010) in serum and brain was reported. Inhibition of AChE activity in IMI and CBZ treatment groups was noticed in the present study. This indicates an increase in ACh level for long-term responsible behavior disturbances such as depression and a

decrease in muscle strength and motor activity. Earlier experiments have shown that the concentration of pesticides and their metabolites in plasma and the brain are usually associated with the extent of neuronal damage (Nagata, et al., 1996). IMI exposure caused necrosis of Purkinje cells with loss of dendrites and granules in the cerebellum granular layer and declines in spontaneous locomotive activity and neuromuscular control (Zhu et al., 2001; Bhardwaj et al., 2010; Lonare et al., 2014). A significant decrease in spontaneous and force locomotor activity and a stimulatory effect on pain parameters in mice exposed to IMI and CBZ in the present study were noticed. This could be due to bio-accumulation of IMI, CBZ, or its metabolites in the brain responsible for brain damage. Neuronal damage in the brain has been clearly noticed in IMI and CBZ-treated mice than in the combined-treated mice. Similarly, bioaccumulation of IMI in the brain with direct intraperitoneal administration and neurotoxicity characterised by declines in motor or locomotive behavioural changes has been reported (Lee Chao and Casida, 1997).

A mixture is the combination of two or more agents and is categorized as simple or complex. The generated and co-incidental mixtures are always created in an environment and that is countless (Groten et al., 2001; Sexton and Hattis, 2007). Moreover, their impact on animal and human health is more unexpected. They may interact with one another by modifying the magnitude of the response and sometimes completely changing the nature of the toxic effect. Interactions may take place in the toxicokinetic phase and/or in the toxicodynamic phase that may be weaker (antagonistic) or stronger (potentiated, synergistic). The data of generalized and biochemical measurements in the present study revealed that the IMI and CBZ mixture comprised the activity of the concerned enzymes and related determinants. A single compound induced higher values than the corresponding control values, indicative of a positive effect, while compound induced lower values than the corresponding control values, indicative of a negative effect.

The combination (IMI and CBZ) treatment showed a lesser effect on the parameters studied in the present study when compared to the sum of their individual effect. This indicates that the predominant antagonistic effect between them is a similar pattern to that from earlier reports of researchers (Krishnan et al., 1994; Mansour et al., 2001). The interaction between pesticides can be expected either because of common cellular targets or because they may have common metabolic pathways (Rashatwar and Matsumura, 1985; Tardif et al., 1993). The interaction between xenobiotics may vary with metabolism, induction and inhibition and post-translational modification of enzymes. Interactions are of toxico-dynamic, toxico-kinetic interaction or agent-to-agent interaction (Mumtaz et al., 2007, Sexton and Hattis, 2007; Viau, 2010). All the mathematical models are predicting the type of toxicity of the mixture, which is not simple to explain, as the mode of action of many chemicals is unknown and interactive effects may differ even with dose and dose ratio (Spurgeon et al., 2010). Thus, there are several possibilities that cannot be ruled out when exploring the potential reasons for non-additivity or antagonism observed in the combined treatment group in the present study.

Hepatic damage often interferes with CYP-mediated drug metabolism, which might be responsible for the reduced biochemical activity or the non-significant changes seen in the co-treated group. It has been reported that the metabolites of IMI and/or CBZ are equally or even more responsible for producing additive or synergistic effects in the body. IMI is metabolized by two major liver enzymes cytochrome P₄₅₀ (CYP_{3A4}) and cytosolic aldehyde oxidase into nitrosoguanidine (IM-NO) and aminoguanidine (IM-NH₂), which are further converted into 6-chloronicotinic acid and 6-hydroxynicotinic acid (Suchail et al., 2001; Honda et al., 2006). The principal metabolites of CBZ are 5-hydroxy-2-benzimidazole carbamate (5-HBC) and 5,6-hydroxy-2-benzimidazole carbamate N-oxides (5,6-HOBC N-oxides).

These hydroxylated derivatives can undergo further biotransformation through conjugation with glutathione, glucuronide, or sulfate. The secondary ring nitrogen can also form N-oxide derivatives (Monson, 1990). Tissue accumulation of CBZ and its metabolites has a major influence on its toxicological activity and accounts for its relatively low mammalian toxicity in the pure state (Krechniak & Kłosowska, 1986). CBZ metabolites are distributed throughout the body and exhibit slow catabolism, resulting in prolonged deposition in tissues such as the gonads, liver, adrenals, adipose tissue, skin, and other organs (Culik, 1981). Repeated administration of IMI at high doses has been shown to induce hepatic and CNS damage in mice. Six metabolites in the hippocampus and ten in the liver have been reported to contribute to early motor dysfunction and hepatic injury (Zheng et al., 2020).

In the present study, the combined treatment group showed lower activity in various parameters than expected. This could be due to impaired metabolite formation or prolonged persistence of metabolites in vital tissues, leading to altered or reduced toxicity. Another possible explanation is that one compound may enhance the metabolic inactivation and elimination of the other. Alternatively, IMI and CBZ may possess independent mechanisms of action and target sites that function autonomously, thereby preventing any additive or synergistic interaction. No exaggerated additive or potentiation response was observed when IMI and CBZ were administered together through dietary exposure. It is therefore difficult to propose an exact mechanism underlying the observed antagonism or lack of synergism when IMI and CBZ were co-exposed.

Conclusion

Environmental contaminants have a significant impact on the health and productivity of animals and plants. When organisms are exposed to more than one environmental toxicant, one compound may influence the effects of another through various ADME (absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion) processes. Such interactions can lead to additivity, potentiation, synergism, or antagonism, ultimately resulting in unexpected outcomes. In this study, a hypothesis was tested in which two environmental toxicants from different categories carbendazim (CBZ) and imidacloprid (IMI), which have independent mechanisms of action, were administered to mice through their regular feed. After the completion of the sub-acute exposure period, alterations in biochemical and central nervous system (CNS)-related parameters were evaluated. An interaction index was then calculated for the indicator parameters. Based on the studied parameters and the calculated interaction index, it was concluded that the individual exposure to CBZ or IMI produces dose-dependent toxic effects. However, their combined exposure does not result in additive or synergistic toxicological effects. These findings rule out the possibility of enhanced toxicity due to the combined exposure of CBZ and IMI and suggest that both compounds act independently without influencing each other's toxicity.

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Author Contributions

SB, MKL, MS, SD and VKD conceived and conducted the study; wrote and approved the manuscript.

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